

CENTRE FOR DRYLAND AGRICULTURE
BAYERO UNIVERSITY, KANO

and

Department of Agronomy

Rice Value Chain Training Module and Course Content

Agro-Processing, Productivity Enhancement and Livelihood
Improvement Support Project Women and Youth Empowerment
Programme.

September 2019

Content

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MODULE 1: RICE PRODUCTION

1.1 OBJECTIVES

1. Identify and explain best agronomic practices in rice production
2. Acquire rice production skill

1.2 INTRODUCTION

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) is one of the most important crops that provide food for about half of the world population, particularly in Asia, Africa and Latin America where the demand for rice is a top priority. In Nigeria, rice constitutes a major part of the diet across each region of the country. Rice is cultivated on 1.8 million hectare with average grain yield of 3.0 t/ha for lowland and 1.5 t/ha for upland. Its cultivation cut across major agro-ecological zones, which ranges from the mangrove ecology of Niger Delta in the coastal areas to the dry zones of the Sahel in the north. Rice has consistently increased in demand and has assumed strategic importance in Nigeria's food security agenda. The increase in demand for rice in Nigeria is attributed to high population growth rate, rapid urbanization and rising incomes. Increase in national rice demand has triggered an increase in domestic production in the last decade. However, demand still exceeds production and large quantities of rice are imported to meet demand at a huge cost in foreign currency. Productivity in rice production must be increased to attain rice self-sufficiency and future demands resulting from population growth.

1.3 PRINCIPLES AND PRACTICES OF RICE PRODUCTION

1.3.1 Ecological Requirements:

Rice is growing under varying conditions that is difficult to define the climate that is more suitable for its development. This is mainly due to the great diversity of its cultivars. Rice required a high growing temperature of about 30 – 32⁰C, the minimum temperature for germination is 18⁰C for tropical varieties and 10 - 12⁰C for subtropical. Rice does not tolerate frost at any stage of growth, long period of sunshine is essential for high yield, however, modern cultivars are mostly day neutral or have only a slight reaction to the photoperiod. The optimum rainfall requirement for upland or dry land rice is 250 – 1500mm evenly distributed during the growing period. Rice requires a heavy soil that holds water with a pH range of 4.5 – 8.

1.3.2 Site/Land Selection:

During rice production, certain guidelines should be followed during land selection: There are two major physical criteria to be considered which are as follows;

- i. **Source of water:** water is a vital for plant growth, and can be used to control weed especially in upland rice. Therefore, farmers should avoid highly drought prone areas, as well as very deep ditches (to get rid of too much water). Farmers should choose gentle slopping land for easy drainage, and a fairly flat land for ease of water distribution.
- ii. **Soil type:** Rice can be grown on different types of soil- from sandy loam to heavy clay. However, sandy soils should be avoided. Select a naturally fertile land, with moderate organic matter. Avoid highly iron-toxic soils if lowland and avoid iron deficient and acid soils if upland.

1.3.3 Variety Selection

While selecting the rice variety, care should be taken to select the varieties preferred by the farmers in a particular area. Healthy and uniform sized seeds from a reliable source should be selected. Seeds of the rice variety should be genetically pure with high germination percentage and vigour, and the selected variety should be suitable for the soil condition in the selected field.

1.3.4 Improved rice varieties that have market value in Nigeria

Lowland:

1. FARO 44: early maturing (100-115) days, for shallow swamps and irrigated ecology, long narrow grains grained
2. FARO 52: medium maturity (120-135 days) medium deep swamps and irrigated ecology, long narrow grains
3. FARO 57: medium maturity (120-135 days), medium deep swamps and irrigated ecology medium grain size

4. FARO 60: early maturing (100-115) days, for shallow swamps and irrigated ecology, long narrow grains grained
5. FARO 61: early maturing (100-115) days, for shallow swamps and irrigated ecology, long narrow grains grained.
6. Others are; FAR015, FAR027, FAR028, ITA 212, ITA 222, ITA 306, SIPI 692033, NERICA, etc.

Upland:

1. FARO 58, Early maturing (100-110 days) narrow medium grain size
2. FARO 59, Early maturity (100-110 days) narrow medium grain size
3. Others are; ITA 257, ITA 150, etc.

1.3.5 Land Preparation

The field should be ploughed thoroughly without any lumps. Green manure crops can be raised in the field in order to enhance the nutrient content of the soil if soil is known to be deficient in fertilizer. Organic manures like farm yard manure, compost and vermin-compost can be used to enhance the soil fertility. Field should be irrigated well within three days of sowing to avoid hardness of the soil.

- a. **For direct seeded rice:** Plough and harrow twice a week or two later when the rains are stable. Remove stables and burry vegetation very well. Level the field properly before seeding.
- b. **For transplanted rice:** Plough the field with early rains. Puddle when there is sufficient water in the field and raise nursery at the same time now remove stables that did not rot and level properly for transplanting when the seedlings are less or 21 days old. If necessary create bunds across gradients dividing the field into section.

1.3.5.1 Advantages of proper land preparation

- ✓ Levelling = improved water coverage in lowland and reduced erosion in upland
- ✓ Bounding increases water distribution and retention

- ✓ Increased reliability of direct seeding (reduces labour by 30 person per days)
- ✓ Reduces weeds up to 40%
- ✓ Eliminate volunteer crop, first stage of seed mixture

1.3.6 Seed preparation (cleaning before sowing):

Salt solution can be used to remove the chaffy seeds from good seeds through the following steps;

- ✓ Take some water in a vessel and drop an egg in it.
- ✓ Keep adding salt to it slowly until the egg reaches the surface of the water.
- ✓ When the seeds are dropped in this water, the good quality seeds will sink into the water.
- ✓ Remove the unviable seeds that float on the surface of the water.
- ✓ Wash the selected seeds in good water for 2 - 3 times to remove the salt deposits.
- ✓ If this is not done, the germination capacity of the seeds will be affected.
- ✓ By this method, the unviable seeds can be removed completely.
- ✓ This method should be followed when there is more of chaff.

1.3.6.1 Sowing:

Planting the crop on time will help produce a fast-growing, uniform crop that will have higher yields and will be better able to compete with weeds and pests. The best time to plant depends on the locality, variety, water availability, and the best harvest time. Rice can either be transplanted from a nursery or direct-seeded in the field. Transplanted crops will normally take less time in the production field but 10–15 days longer for the total crop duration. In both cases, a well-prepared seedbed is needed. There are two ways of establishing rice crop viz; direct seeding and nursery.

1. **Direct seeding:** Rice seeds are directly sown in the field when there is assurance of seed viability (80 -95%). There are two types of direct seeding depending on the ecology and moisture content of the soil (i.e. wet and dry direct seeding).

- **Wet direct seeding:** in this method, farmers are advised to follow the following steps while sowing the crop;
 - ✓ Pre-germination of seed- soak the seed for 24 hours and then drain for 24 hours in the shade before broadcasting evenly over the water-covered soil surface.
 - ✓ Broadcast pre-germinated seed at 100 kg ha^{-1}
 - ✓ Allow surface water to drain or percolate naturally into soil
 - ✓ Keep soil surface moist by adding water
 - ✓ Add permanent water at 10–15 days after establishment or at 2–3leaf stage.
 - ✓ Apply basal fertilizer after permanent water is added.
- **Dry direct seeding:** the following steps should be adopted in dry direct seeding;
 - ✓ Hand broadcast dry seed at 100 kg ha^{-1} or machine drill seed at 80 kg ha^{-1} and 20mm depth
 - ✓ Apply basal fertilizer through the seed drill
 - ✓ Cover broadcast seed and fertilizer with a light harrowing
 - ✓ Flash flood until 15 days after emergence or 2-leaf stage then adds permanent water.

1.3.6.3 Nursery bed operations for transplanted rice:

For transplanting, seedlings are raised in either a dry or wet nursery. In dry nursery the land is well-cultivated and fertilized with well-rotted farmyard manure. Nursery beds are made 1-1.5m wide and of appropriate length. The beds are slightly raised. For planting one hectare of field, seedlings are raised in nurseries of about 350-500m² in area. Adequate fertilizer should be applied before sowing. Pre-soaked seeds are broadcast or drilled (10cm apart) in the prepared nurseries at the rate of 1-2kg per 20-35m². The seed is covered with 2-3cm soil.

A wet nursery is the more common method. The land is flooded and puddled and fertilized (farmyard manure). Nursery beds are made as for dry nursery. They are also slightly raised. Pre-soaked, sometimes pre-germinated seeds are broadcast on mud at the rate of 25 kg per 350-500m² of nursery beds and water is allowed to stand continuously on the beds after the seedlings are about 15

cm high. Seedlings grow quickly and are ready for transplanting in 25-30 days, when they are 15-30 cm tall and have developed 5-7 leaves (depending on the variety).

Sometimes the seeds are germinated on strips of polythene or other materials (impermeable layer such as banana leaves, plastic sheet) which keep the root system on the surface. Such seedlings are easier to raise and are ready for transplanting in 10-14 days. This system is referred to as the Dapog method. A 20-25m² seed bed is enough for 1 hectare.

For either of the systems it is important to sow thinly as this will encourage sturdy and healthy growth of the seedlings and savings in seeds. The sown seeds are to be covered with grass mulch and removed on the 7th day after the seedlings must have emerged.

1.3.7 Transplanting:

It is advisable to site nursery beds near the cultivation area as the weight of the seedlings is quite cumbersome. Transplanting is done mostly by hand but it can also be done mechanically. Usually 2-3 seedlings are transplanted at each position at 20 – 25cm x 20 – 25cm inter and intra row spacing, respectively. Older seedlings grow more slowly than younger ones and they may result in prolonged maturity, reduced tillering capacity with consequent reduction in yield. A day or two before transplanting, the soil is heavily watered to make uprooting of the seedlings easy. Seedlings should be pulled out carefully, the root washed, tied into bundles before transplanting to the field. About 3 days before transplanting a rotavator is used to break the soil into very fine particles. The soil should be drained to improve aeration.

1.3.8 Weed Management

Weeds compete directly with the rice plants and reduce rice yield. Each 1 kg dry matter of weeds is equivalent to 1 kg grain loss. Weeds cause most yield loss within the first 20–50 days after crop establishment. Weeding after panicle initiation may also be important to prevent weeds shedding seeds in future crops. Two hoe or hand weeding at 2-3 weeks and 5-6 WAS or WAT will be adequate. Herbicide can also be used to control weed in rice, some common Herbicides include: Butachlor @ 1.5 kga.i/ha PE, Butachlor + Propanil @ (1.5 + 3.0) kg a.i/ha POE

@ 15 DAP, Propanil + Oxadiazon @ 2.5 kg a.i/ha POE @ 15 DAP, Propanil + Bentazon @ 3.0 kg a.i/ha POE @ 15 DAP.

For Effective weed management in rice, the following steps should be practice:

- ✓ Ploughing and harrowing in fallow should be undertaken at least 10–14 days apart or after rain.
- ✓ Good land levelling reduces weed growth because most weeds have trouble germinating under water.
- ✓ Select varieties which have early vigour.
- ✓ Use clean rice seed which is free of weed seeds.
- ✓ Apply permanent water early — weeds cannot germinate under water.
- ✓ First weeding begins within 2–3 weeks after establishment and the second in another 2–3 weeks. Weed before fertilizer application.
- ✓ Using herbicides. Identify the weed correctly and use the appropriate herbicide as recommended on the label.
- ✓ Spray when the weeds are small.
- ✓ Apply pre-emergence herbicides after planting prior to establishment.
- ✓ Apply post-emergence herbicides after emergence being careful of crop damage.
- ✓ Herbicides are poisonous; if they are not used properly they can cause health and environment problems. Label them clearly and keep them out of children's reach.
- ✓ Always use protective clothing when spraying.
- ✓ Do not wear raincoats when spraying as this increases sweating.

Also, good water management helps reduce weed competition, which not only increases yields but also improves grain quality by reducing dockage levels and reducing moisture differentials between weed seeds and grain.

1.3.9 Fertilizer application:

Most soils provide only limited amount of nutrients to the crop, therefore fertilizers need to be applied to increase grain yield. In some cases, fertilizers are also added to improve the soil's physical condition. The amount and type of fertilizer applied are determined on the assumption that 1 ton of grain will remove 15 kg nitrogen (N), 2–3 kg phosphorus (P), and 15–20 kg potassium (K). These base rates need to be modified according to the soil type, the season, the crop condition, prevailing weather conditions, and efficiency of application. In Nigeria, the recommended fertilizer rate for rice is 70-120kgN, 30-40kg P₂O₅ and 30-40 kg K₂O per hectare depending on the fertility status of the soil and the ecology. For efficient fertilizer use:

- ✓ Use organic fertilizer (manure, compost, straw, husk, plant leaves) whenever possible, especially in nurseries.
- ✓ Apply fertilizer according to soil type and expected yield. As a guide, a 2 t/ha yield on clay loam soil will require 20 kg N and 5 kg P. Sandy soils may require another 10–15 kg K. Double these recommendations for a 3 t/ha expected yield.
- ✓ Apply all P, K, and 10% N evenly and incorporate just before seeding or transplanting. For direct seeded broadcast crops, it is okay to apply 10–14 days after establishment when there is water in the field.
- ✓ Apply remaining N (urea) in 2 equal portions at 30 days and 50–60 days (panicle initiation) after emergence.
- ✓ In established crops, apply chemical fertilizer only in standing water and evenly across the whole field.
- ✓ Do not apply high rates of fertilizer for traditional varieties as they may have limited response and cause lodging.
- ✓ Do not use chemical fertilizer if you need more than 5 kg paddy to pay for 1 kg of fertilizer.
- ✓ Inorganic fertilizers must be stored in a dry and cool place that is out of children's reach.

1.3.10 Water Management:

Water availability largely determines the potential crop yield. For a crop to continue to grow, the water supply needs to be similar or a little above evaporation. In an efficient system, each 1 kg of grain produced will require a minimum of 2,000 liters or 2 m³ of water. Good water control increases crop yields and grain quality as well as improving the efficiency of other inputs such as fertilizer, herbicide, and pesticides. To maximize water-use efficiency:

- ✓ Maintain the bunds;
- ✓ Level the fields;
- ✓ Puddle the fields where possible;
- ✓ Use direct-seeding techniques;
- ✓ Use short-duration crops; and
- ✓ Harvest on time.

1.3.10.1 Water quality

Good-quality water is necessary to maximize crop growth. The rice plant is susceptible to salinity especially at the seedling stage and during the panicle development stage from panicle initiation to booting. Symptoms of salt toxicity include “firing” of leaves and reduced dry matter production. The effects of high salinity during panicle development are less obvious as there is little leaf effect, but florets and grain numbers per panicle are reduced greatly reducing yield.

1.4 PEST AND DISEASES OF RICE AND THEIR MANAGEMENT

Farmers lose an estimated average of 37% of their rice crop to pests and diseases every year.

In addition to good crop management, timely and accurate diagnosis can significantly reduce losses. The best control for pests and disease problems is prevention. To limit pest and disease incidences in a rice crop, the following recommendations can be followed:

- ✓ Practice good cleaning of equipment.
- ✓ Clean the field between seasons by managing stubbles and ratoons, and by maintaining and repairing bunds.

- ✓ Use clean seeds and resistant varieties.
- ✓ Certified seed is recommended. If certified seed is not available, use clean seed having no discoloured seeds, weed seeds or other rice varieties mixed in.
- ✓ Use short-duration and resistant cultivars to decrease insect pest populations.
- ✓ Plant at the same time as your neighbors (or within a 2 week window) to minimize insect, disease, bird, and rat pressure on individual fields.
- ✓ Do not over apply fertilizer. Following specific fertilizer recommendations is important because high nitrogen can increase susceptibility to certain pests and diseases.
- ✓ Encourage natural pest enemies.
- ✓ Overuse of pesticide is common among farmers and can actually lead to pest outbreaks.
- ✓ Natural enemies of rice pests are killed when pesticides are applied which can lead to a pest outbreak.
- ✓ Do not apply pesticide within 40 days of planting.
- ✓ Rice crops can recover from early damage without affecting yield.
- ✓ Get appropriate information on specific diseases that require early management.

If there are pest or disease incidences in the crop, it is important to diagnose the problem accurately. When deciding to use a chemical for pest and disease control, it is important to:

- ✓ Use well-maintained spray equipment that has been properly calibrated;
- ✓ Apply the dosage recommended by the manufacturer; and
- ✓ Follow the safety precautions for mixing and spray applications.

1.4.1 Diseases:

- ✓ Watch out for the incidence of diseases insect and vertebrate pests.
- ✓ Blast is the most dangerous rice disease especially under drought conditions
- ✓ It can reduce yield significantly if not total loss
- ✓ There could seedling blast, usually overcome when moisture level improves; leaf blast can burn down the entire crop to no grain formation

- ✓ Neck blast results in poor grain filling and poor quality grains. Use fungicides when early symptoms appear
- ✓ Other diseases are brown spot, usually less dangerous but can cause serious poor grain quality
- ✓ bacterial leaf blight, sheath rot, leaf scald and false smut are other disease that can be encountered in the rice field

1.4.2 Insect Pest:

- ✓ African rice gall midge is the most dangerous insect pest in Nigeria and can cause yield loss beyond 80 %.
- ✓ The galls are like onion shoot occurring from seedlings to maximum tillering stages
- ✓ The gall cannot pull off, unlike the stem borers dead heart or white head
- ✓ Stem borers though predominant do not cause much damage, tillers are usually replaced
- ✓ Another dangerous insect pest is leaf miners, destroying green leaves and resulting in feathery whitish leaves
- ✓ They winter on alternative host and can be checked by spraying insecticides on the ponds around the farms before crop establishment
- ✓ Grain suckers such as *Asparvia* produce symptoms similar to that of bird damage at milky stage
- ✓ The can physically be seen on the young panicles in the field.

1.4.3 Control

The choice of control method depends on a number of factors, the most important of which are economic and ecological. Appropriate pest and diseases control measures should be cheap and result in financial benefit. They should also have a solid ecological basis with little or no disruptive effect on the environment.

Figure: Rice Field

Figure: Rice Field almost ready for harvest

Figure: Rice at maturity

1.5 HARVESTING OF RICE

Harvesting the crop on time is very important to maximize yields and grain quality. Crops harvested too early will have many unfilled and immature grains. Immature grains break easily when milled and will not germinate when used for seed. If crops are harvested late, heavy losses will occur through shattering and bird attacks. Quality will also decrease due to grain weathering, resulting in breakage and downgrading due to undesirable grain colour.

Crops should be harvested when:

- ✓ Grain moisture is between 20–22%, which is normally about 30 days after flowering;
- ✓ 80–85% of the grains are straw-coloured (changed from green to golden colour)
- ✓ Grains in the lower part of the panicle are hard, not soft; and
- ✓ Grains are firm but not easily broken when squeezed between the teeth.

After cutting, maximize grain quality by:

- ✓ Ensuring the panicles do not touch the ground or lay in water;
- ✓ Minimizing the time the cut panicles remain in large bundles in the field -thresh within 24 hours of cutting;
- ✓ Drying the grains as soon as possible after threshing;
- ✓ Turning or stirring the grains at least once every hour when sun drying to achieve uniform drying;
- ✓ Sun drying on tarpaulins or clean drying pads;
- ✓ Keeping the thickness of the grain layer at 3–5 cm;
- ✓ Covering the grain on hot days during mid-day to prevent over-heating, and covering immediately if it starts raining;
- ✓ Cleaning the grain by repeated winnowing after drying; and
- ✓ Storing the rice in a cool, dry, and clean area — preferably in sealed containers for seed.

Figure: Winnowing of Rice

Figure: Mechanized Rice Threshing

1.6 STORAGE OF RICE

Rice is best stored as paddy because the husk provides some protection against insects and helps prevent grain quality deterioration. A safe storage system will prevent the grain from getting wet after drying and also give protection from insects, rodents, and birds. Rice can be stored for longer periods if:

- ✓ Moisture content is maintained at less than 14% for grain and 12% for seed;
- ✓ Grain is protected from insects, rodents, and birds; and
- ✓ Grain is protected from re-wetting by rain or from the surrounding air.

A rule of thumb for seed is that the life of the seed will be halved for every 1% increase in moisture content or a 5°C increase in storage temperature above recommended levels.

MODULE II: RICE PROCESSING:

1.1 OBJECTIVES

1. identify the types of rice processing
2. Acquire rice parboiling and milling skills
3. Identify rice parboiling and milling equipment

1.2 INTRODUCTION

Olukosi and Isitor (1990) defined processing as the conversion of a commodity from its raw state to a form more acceptable to the buyers or to the next stage in the distribution chain. According to Jones (1992), processing is beneficial in that it helps to convert agricultural products into forms more suitable or desirable for human consumption. It also makes food safer by removing, inhibiting or killing pathogenic microorganisms and also to inactivate toxic factors. Processing is a form of changing activity which may be necessary to improve the value of some products or to increase their shelf life through processing (Adekanye, 1998). The activities of food processing are concerned with the addition of value, which result from changing the form of the primary product. Processing methods are mainly traditional, intermediate and improved or advanced technologies (Olukosi and Isitor, 1990).

1.3 RICE PARBOILING

Parboiling is the central activity in rice processing and an important operation that determines rice quality. Parboiling is the hydrothermal treatment of raw paddy before milling and consists of three major activities namely, soaking, steaming and drying. Pre parboiling operations like sieving paddy before washing and soaking improves quality of paddy. Soaking involves allowing the rice kernel to absorb water so as to increase its moisture content. There are basically two methods of soaking, namely, warm water soaking in which the paddy is heated in warm water and allowed to soak overnight; and hot water soaking in which paddy is heated with hot water and allowed to soak for about 5 hours. After soaking, the rice is removed for drying. The method of parboiling is presented in the figure.

Figure: Rice parboiling and drying

Figure: Rice milling

1.4 RICE MILLING

Paddy or the rice grain consists of the hull or husk (18–28%) and the brown rice (72–82%). Brown rice consists of an outer layer called bran (6-7%), the germ or embryo (2-3%), and the edible portion – the endosperm (89-94%) (NCRI, 1997). Rice milling operation is the separation of the husk (de-husking or de-hulling) and the bran (polishing) to produce the edible portion for consumption. Although, in theory mill recovery is between 71 and 73%, in practical terms, however, only 68 to 70% is obtained from a good variety of paddy. Sources of losses during milling are many, but could be greatly reduced with the adoption of a combination of technical efficiency enhancing factors. Three systems of rice milling can be identified in Nigeria. These are the traditional or hand pounding system, the small mill processing system and the large mill processing system (Ochigbo and Gbabo, 2004). The hand- pounding system of processing rice paddy which is still used by some village rice farmers in Nigeria is a process of pounding parboiled paddy in a mortar to separate husks and bran from the grains. The rice is winnowed to remove the husks. This system is very slow and labour intensive and the final product contains a high percentage of broken grains and foreign bodies.

The small rice mills are the most predominant of the three processing systems (Akpokodje *et al.*, 2003). These can be found in major rice processing areas across Nigeria. About 85 percent of Nigerian rice is processed using the small milling system. This system of processing involves the use of mechanized milling units (operating the old concho disc technology) with a maximum and minimum capacity of 600 and 200-300 tonnes per day respectively. Some of these machines are diesel powered while others are electrically energized. The use of diesel powered engines is not unconnected with the epileptic power supply in the country. Presently, most small rice mills operate at about 1 tonne/hour. The final product of the small mills is generally superior to that processed under the traditional hand pounding system even though it also contains a high percentage of broken grains.

Milling rice paddy removes the husk and bran layer to produce white rice. Rice is best milled at 13–14% moisture content. Best results are attained when the process is completed in a number of stages. Grain temperatures should not exceed 45°C during the process. An efficient mill removes the husk (20%), the bran or meal (8–10%), and leaves 70% as white rice. Rice grown in irrigated systems should attain 60% white rice as head rice (unbroken, white kernels) and rain fed systems 40–50% as head rice. Rice is milled in several ways.

1. Hand pounding using a mortar with a pestle results in very high numbers of broken rice and leaves brown rice (meal layer still attached). Cleaning of the husk is done by winnowing.
2. A one-step milling process where the husk and the bran are removed in one pass and white rice is produced directly from the paddy. The single-pass rice mill is an adaptation of the Engle berg coffee huller. This process results in many broken kernels, low white rice recovery (50–55%), and head rice yields less than 30%. The fine broken are often mixed in with the bran and the ground rice husk.
3. A two-step milling process where the husk and the bran are removed separately. These mills are often called compact rice mills and, in many countries, have superseded the Engle berg mill. The two-stage mill has separate hulling and polishing processes. Rubber rollers remove the husk and the brown rice is polished with a steel friction whitener. These mills have a capacity of 0.5–1 t/hour paddy input and are often used for custom milling in rural areas. The milling performance of the compact rice mill is superior to the Single-pass huller with milling recoveries normally above 60%.
4. A multi-stage milling process where rice passes through a number of different operations. The milling process in larger commercial mills combines a number of operations and produces higher quality and higher yields of white rice from paddy rice. The process involves:

- ✓ Pre-cleaning the paddy prior to milling;

- ✓ Removing the husk or outer layer from the paddy;
- ✓ Polishing the brown rice to remove the bran layer;
- ✓ Separating the broken grains from the whole kernels;
- ✓ Bagging the milled rice; and
- ✓ Managing the by-products.

Most modern milling machines combine the hulling and polishing processes. To further improve the appearance and quality of the rice, extra polishing equipment and color sorting equipment is used. In a standard rice milling process, the flow goes from:

Paddy precleaning & Destoning -> Paddy Separation -> Paddy Dehulling or Dehusking -> Paddy Separation -> Rice Polishing -> Rice Grading -> Rice Polishing -> Color Sorting and finally packaging.

It is important to ensure that the parboiling process is done well, and the paddy moisture content is between 14% and 13% before milling. This is to affect discoloration and breakage of rice. A moisture content meter is used to measure the moisture content of the grain.

Figure: A simple Rice Mill

Figure: Rice Mills.